

A Trend Analysis of Intra-BRICS Imports

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Abstract

The potent association of the world's top developing market countries—Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa—goes by the abbreviation BRICS. The BRICS countries account for 16% of world imports, 19% of global imports, and 19% of both incoming and exiting direct investment, respectively, recognizing the BRICS countries' growing political and economic influence on the world stage. One of the main goals of the current study is to examine the import and import interdependence among the BRICS group of countries in light of the increased efforts made by the leaders of BRICS states to improve mutual trade and build BRICS. The paper studies the trends¹ of import partner share of each BRICS nation towards the member nations since 2008 as it held its first formal summit in the year 2009.

Keywords: Intra-BRICS, import inter-dependence, Import Share, Import Share, Trade Intensity.

Introduction

The term “BRIC” was coined by Jim O’ Neil in the paper titled as “Building Better Global Nations” in the year 2001. This paper highlighted the rising importance of BRIC nations in the world economic framework. It concludes that the BRIC share in the world GDP² is set to rise over the next decade and each nation set to grow more than the other groups such as G7. The group’s founding summit took place in Yekaterinburg in 2009. (Russia). It concentrated on the state of the world economy and signalled the need for a varied, stable, and predictable global reserve currency. Since then, there have been 12 summits where the member countries have reached agreements on economic cooperation for mutual benefit. The BRICS countries collectively account for around 26.7% of the world’s land area, 41.5% of the world’s population, and 23.2% of global GDP. The various countries emphasise the value of trade in moving the economic cooperation agenda ahead because they collectively account for 20% of global commerce. An earlier analysis showed that commerce between the BRICS has increased since

¹ Trends-The general way in which a particular situation is changing or developing.” The Financial Times’ glossary of terms – ft.com/lexicon.

² World GDP- The gross world product (GWP) is the combined gross national income of all the countries in the world.(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gross_world_product)

2009 and has shifted from wealthy countries to their counterparts in poorer countries. Consequently, it is evident from the background information above that intra-BRICS trade has been growing since 2009. Hence, it is imperative to find the share of BRICS nations in the overall trade of each member nations since 2009, to seek the importance of the group in the trade flows of member nations.

Objectives

1. To study the trend of share of BRICS in the total imports of each member nation from 2009 to 2019.
2. To estimate the compound annual growth rate of Intra-BRICS import share for the period of 2009 to 2019.

Period of the study and Source of Data

To seek the trends of the import share, this study chooses the 10 years of data from 2009 to 2019. The study uses only time series secondary data collected from the World Integrated Trade Solution Statistics (WITS), World Bank Data.

Limitations

The present study is restricted to analyze trade relations of BRICS nations only. This study uses only secondary data and limited for the period of 10 years and uses import share as variables to study the importance of member nations in the total trade of the member nation concerned.

Methodology

The present paper uses a simple trend-analysis graph showing the values of import share of the respective nations for the period of 10 years. To compute the values of compound annual growth rate of import share for the respective nations, it uses the formula given below as-

$$\text{CAGR} = [\text{Ending Value} / \text{Beginning Value}]^{1/n}$$

Review of Literature

1. **Rahman, M., Fatima, Z., & Rahman, N. (2020)** used data from the years 2000 to 2017 to study the intra-BRICS trade flows and relations by adopting the gravity model of trade. According to the findings, trade would be impacted by 0.55% for every 1% rise in the GDP of importing and importing nations. According to the study, imports will rise by 1.26% and 2.30%, respectively, for every 1% growth in the size of the importing and importing markets. Furthermore, given that the BRICS countries are varied and have disparate per capita incomes, this analysis suggests that they adhere to the Hecksher-Ohlin Model of Trade.

2. **Rani and Kumar (2018)** assessed the impact and influence of fiscal growth, trade openness,

domestic investment, and foreign investment on the economic growth of the BRICS countries using a panel data set covering the years 1993 to 2015. Fiscal success was measured using proxies such as the supply of money as a proportion of GDP and the supply of domestic credit as a percentage of GDP to the private sector. The trade/GDP ratio was sometimes used as a stand-in for openness. Gross capital creation as a percentage of GDP and inward FDI as a percentage of GDP served as stand-ins for domestic and foreign investments, respectively. An equilibrium link between the underlying components was found by the inquiry. The magnitude of the equilibrium or long-term coefficients was also examined in the study using the FMOLS and DOLS methods. The results showed that the money supply, gross capital creation, and the trade-to-GDP ratio all had a positive and substantial influence on economic growth. On the other side, it has been demonstrated that inward FDI has a negative and significant impact on a country's growth performance. As a result, for the BRICS nations to experience the benefits of growth and wealth, lowering trade barriers and bolstering financial markets are essential.

3. **Solanki Y.P.(2017)** reported that the BRICS countries' percentage of global imports increased from 8.08% in 2001 to 19.31% in 2015, with China accounting for 14% of that total. On the other hand, the BRICS countries' proportion of global imports also rose in 2015, from 6.60% to 15.21%. Despite China being the greatest intra-regional importer in terms of absolute amount of trade, it was discovered that between 2006 and 2015, Brazil had the highest intra-BRICS import share and China had the lowest. Brazil, Russia, and South Africa have all seen an increase in the proportion of their domestic imports to their total imports between 2006 and 2015, whilst China and India have seen a decline. However, the analysis suggested that between 2006 and 2015, all of the member countries' intra-BRICS import shares increased, indicating a higher import dependency. In the current study, the values of the intra-BRICS import and import intensity indices for each member country from the years 2006 to 2015 were calculated. It was discovered that the overall intra-BRICS import intensity index had decreased from 0.63 in 2001 to 0.50 in 2015, and that the intra-BRICS import index had exhibited a similar trend, falling from 1.04 in 2001 to 0.92 in 2015.

4. **Exim bank of india working paper (2016)** The article examines the importance of the BRICS nations, which account for 17.2% of global commerce, 22.5% of global production, and 40% of global population. According to the report, China has contributed significantly to intra-BRICS trade, which it accounts for about half of. South Africa, India, Brazil, and Russia came after this. When it comes to the case of India, it reveals a sharp increase in trade deficits with BRICS countries, with China being the largest, and a decline in India's import intensity towards the same countries.

5. **Singh K. (2016)** examined the changes in the proportion of the BRICS countries in global commerce from 2001 to 2015, as well as the levels of intra-BRICS trade between each of the BRICS countries. In addition, the intra-BRICS trade as a percentage of overall BRICS trade climbed from 6.03% to 12.12%, doubling the BRICS countries' contribution to global trade.

China supplied the majority of the 17.25% share of BRICS countries in global trade, or 12.08%. The research also found that while global commerce with BRICS as a whole has grown faster than intra-BRICS trade, the intensity of trade within the BRICS has declined from 0.82% in 2001 to 0.70% in 2015.

6. **Bipul Chatterjee, Purna Chandra Jena and Surendar Singh(2014)** This study used the Finger-Kreinin Index, Relative Import Competitive Pressure Index, and Revealed Comparative Advantage methodologies to examine the level of competitiveness, comparative advantage, and trade similarity across the BRICS countries with a focus on India. According to the study, it was discovered that: India and China were not fighting for the Brazilian market; Brazil and India faced only mild rivalry in China; and FKI suggests that India and China's imports were comparable to those of the Russian markets. In Russian markets, India-China import competitiveness ranged from moderate to high; FKI ranged from 0.01 to 0.21, indicating that India and Russia competed strongly in the South African market; Trade openness(import + imports as % of GDP) for India rose from 27% in 2001 to 57% in 2013.

7. **Castro T.(2010)** In this study, the trade intensity and intra-intensity index were examined using data from 1995 to 2009. Trade Intensity(S): which indicates the relative significance of a trading partner. Nevertheless, to compare trade shares, they utilise the Intra Intensity Index (Iij), which is defined as a ratio using the trade shares of partner countries I and j's total trade as the numerator and the trade shares of partner country j's total trade as the denominator. $I = \frac{T_{ij}}{T_{iw}, T_{jw}, \text{ and } T_i}$. They discovered that the Intra-Intensity Index (ITI) displayed the characteristics as Brazil and Russia did, where ITI peaked in 1999 and then began to decline starting in 2000. Since that time, ITI has been trending lower.

Data Analysis and Findings

Import share is the percentage of imports going to a partner to total imports of a country/region. It is computed as the dollar value of imports of country/region i to country/region j expressed as a percentage share of the dollar value of imports of country/region i to the world. A higher share indicates a higher degree of integration between partner countries/regions.

The significance of the BRICS nations in the total trade of each member nation can be ascertained by evaluating the trends of Intra-BRICS¹ import share.

Brazil's Import Share with BRICS- Brazil has the highest share in its import with China with an average of 19.5% of its total imports while around 2% with rest of the nations. Seeking the trends of the Brazil's import-partner share from 2009 onwards till 2019 with China got doubled from 13.7% in 2009 to 28.1% in 2019. Considering with India it found to be more or less at 2% without significant change for the 10 years period. Similar trends were observed for the Russia and South Africa where the 10 year average were 1% and 0.5% respectively.(See Table1.1) Computing the compound annual growth rate of import share for Brazil nation remains to be similar with all the member at around 5-10%.

Partner / Year	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
China	13.7285	15.247	17.3078	16.9956	19.0165	18.0437	18.6303	18.967	21.8098	26.7649	28.111
India	2.2321	1.7296	1.2501	2.299	1.2932	2.1274	1.8927	1.7067	2.1389	1.6299	1.232
Russia	1.8749	2.0563	1.6467	1.2948	1.2288	1.7011	1.2894	1.2416	1.2568	0.69	0.7182
South Africa	0.8234	0.6488	0.6564	0.7278	0.7587	0.5445	0.7083	0.7542	0.6933	0.5682	0.5023

Source: World Integrated Trade Solution Statistics (WITS)

Russia's Import Share with BRICS- The share of Brazil in Russian imports rose for about 0.2% points from 2009 to 2019. It showed stable trend without any significant changes in the import partner share for the same. On the other side China which has the highest share in the Russian imports as compared to other member nations, shown a significant rise in the import partner share from 5.5% in 2009 to 13.44% in 2019. Moving ahead to the average share of India and South Africa in Russian imports from 2009 to 2019 was about 1.4% and 0.05% respectively. In addition to it, South Africa and Brazil had shown a negative compound annual growth in the Russia's imports share for the 10 year period (2009-2019).

India's Import Share with BRICS- The share of Brazil in India's imports was about 1.4% on average, being highest for the period of 2012 to 2014 at 2.2% while least during 2016 to 2018 around 0.8%. China's share remained significantly stable for about 5.2% during the 10

¹Intra-BRICS Trade- trade flows within the BRICS member nations.

year period. Similar trends were observed for the Russia and South Africa, as it hovered around at 0.7% and 1.4% respectively showing a stable trends. Moreover, it was observed that compound annual growth rate in the India's import share was negative for all the BRICS member nations except China. It implies that China's share in Indian imports kept rising annually at a rate of 0.09%.

China's Import Share with BRICS- The share of Brazil in China's imports was average around 1.4% from 2009 to 2019 rose by 2-3% points during the same period. India having the highest share in the China's imports around 2.5% on an average for the 10yr period. Next to it, Russia also had significant contribution in Chinese imports with an average of 1.9% for the same period. Moreover, the contribution of South Africa in Chinese imports remained consistent in the range 0.61% to 0.76%. Although the compound annual growth rate in Chinese import share was found to be negative for the member nations.

South Africa's Import Share with BRICS- The share of Brazil in South Africa's imports rose continuously from 0.66% in 2009 to 0.80% till 2015, thereafter it declined for the next three years to 0.49% till 2018. China having the highest share in the South Africa's imports around 10.23% on average for the 10 year period from 2009 to 2019. Next to it, India being the significant contributor in South African imports with an average of 3.99% for the same period. Lastly, Russia's share in South African imports revolved in the range of 0.33% to 0.42%. Moreover, it was observed that compound annual growth rate in the South Africa's import share was negative for all the BRICS member nations except Brazil.

Conclusion

Within the BRICS group of nations China has been the most significant trade partner from the period of 2009 to 2019 as stated above. Moreover, with the detailed analysis of the import

partner share for each member nation we found that it remained more or less stable but kept rising significantly towards China. Brazil has been the third most significant import partner for each BRICS nations, though share of Brazil in member nation imports was following a constant trend. Russia's share in imports of member nations remained low with each nation following a stable trend except China, where it holds the second-most important import partner after India.

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ANNEXURE

Table 1.1: Brazil's Import Share With BRICS												CAGR	Average
Partner/Year	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		
China	12.46	14.08	14.49	15.35	15.56	16.30	17.92	16.99	18.12	19.16	19.89	4.34	16.39
India	1.72	2.33	2.69	2.26	2.65	2.90	2.50	1.80	1.95	2.02	2.40	3.10	2.29
Russia	1.11	1.05	1.30	1.25	1.12	1.32	1.30	1.47	1.75	1.86	2.08	5.89	1.42
South Africa	0.34	0.41	0.40	0.38	0.30	0.32	0.38	0.24	0.32	0.37	0.42	2.05	0.35

Source: Compiled and Computed by the author based on Data available on World Integrated Trade Solution Statistics (WITS)

Table 1.2: Russia's Import Share With BRICS												CAGR	Average
Partner/Year	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		
Brazil	2.05	1.78	1.43	1.06	1.11	1.38	1.60	1.23	1.25	1.03	0.87	-7.50	1.35
China	13.38	17.02	15.69	16.37	16.88	17.74	19.26	22.34	21.9 1	21.74	21.91	4.58	18.57
India	0.89	0.94	0.90	0.96	0.98	1.11	1.24	1.22	1.19	1.34	1.59	5.37	1.12
South Africa	0.19	0.21	0.15	0.22	0.25	0.24	0.32	0.26	0.25	0.33	0.33	5.42	0.25

Source: Compiled and Computed by the author based on Data available on World Integrated Trade Solution Statistics (WITS)

Table 1.3: India's Import Share With BRICS												CAGR	Average
Partner/Year	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		
Brazil	1.09	0.92	0.81	1.10	0.82	1.21	1.05	1.01	1.15	0.91	0.64	-4.77	0.97
China	11.49	11.78	12.00	11.07	11.08	12.68	15.77	16.96	16.20	14.63	14.28	2.00	13.45
Russia	1.29	1.03	0.88	0.94	0.82	0.92	1.16	1.34	1.80	1.38	1.30	0.07	1.17
South Africa	1.89	1.97	2.02	1.64	1.58	1.30	1.61	1.43	1.55	1.33	1.39	-2.78	1.61

Source: Compiled and Computed by the author based on Data available on World Integrated Trade Solution Statistics (WITS)